

**ADVANCED ADMINISTRATIVE LEADERSHIP AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO
THE CHARACTER FORMATION OF THE FACULTY AND STAFF IN A
SECONDARY PUBLIC SCHOOL WITHIN THE 1st DISTRICT
OF SULTAN KUDARAT**

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Advanced Administrative Leadership and its Relationship to the Character Formation of the Faculty and Staff in a Secondary Public School within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of advanced administrative leadership and character formation on the faculty and staff in a secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat. The research aims to evaluate how these leadership practices enhance key areas such as communication, risk management, strategic planning, resource allocation, and delegation of power within the school. Additionally, it examines how character formation influences organizational commitment, career progression, values and attitudes, social environment, and cultural practices among staff members. Data were collected from 114 respondents through surveys and interviews, revealing a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.884$, $p < 0.05$) between advanced administrative leadership practices and character formation. The findings highlight the critical role of effective leadership in fostering a supportive and ethical school environment, which in turn promotes staff satisfaction and student success. This study explores the impact of advanced administrative leadership and character formation on faculty and staff in a secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat. Recommendations include the implementation of targeted professional development programs, improved feedback mechanisms, and initiatives to strengthen ethical and collaborative practices within the school. These strategies aim to create a cohesive and motivated educational community, ultimately contributing to the holistic development of students and the overall excellence in a secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat. The insights gained from this research provide valuable guidance for educational institutions aiming to cultivate an environment that supports both professional and personal growth for their staff and students.

Keywords: *advanced administrative leadership, work system*

Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of educational administration, the role of leadership and character formation has garnered increasing attention for their pivotal influence on organizational effectiveness and student outcomes. Within the context of secondary public schools within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat, the integration of advanced administrative leadership and character development initiatives stands as a potential catalyst for enhancing overall school performance. Recent research emphasizes the crucial role of effective leadership in educational institutions, highlighting its impact on organizational culture, innovation, and student achievement (Huber, 2020). Effective administrative leadership not only shapes the strategic direction of the school but also fosters an environment conducive to the personal and professional growth of both staff and students, ultimately contributing to the institution's success and sustainability.

Additionally, scholarly discourse underscores the significance of character formation in fostering ethical behavior, social responsibility, and academic success among students (Park & Peterson, 2019). As educational institutions strive to cultivate environments conducive to holistic student development and organizational excellence, understanding the nexus between advanced administrative leadership and character formation becomes imperative.

On a national scale, educational institutions are continuously exploring avenues to enhance administrative leadership practices and character development initiatives to cultivate a conducive learning environment and foster holistic student development (Seligman et al., 2018). Acknowledging the pivotal role of effective administrative leadership in shaping organizational culture and driving positive change, schools across the country are increasingly focusing on integrating advanced leadership strategies into their frameworks (Huber, 2020). Concurrently, character formation has gained recognition as a cornerstone of education, with studies highlighting its profound impact on student outcomes and ethical behavior (Park & Peterson, 2019).

Secondary public schools within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat, like many educational institutions, face the challenge of nurturing effective leadership and character development among their stakeholders while optimizing talent management practices. As key institutions in the region, these schools play a crucial role in shaping the educational landscape of Sultan Kudarat. The integration of advanced administrative leadership and character formation initiatives offers a promising avenue for enhancing organizational effectiveness and student outcomes within these schools.

Recent literature underscores the importance of advanced administrative leadership in driving positive change and fostering a culture of excellence in educational institutions (Leithwood et al., 2019). Effective leadership is essential for navigating complex challenges, fostering innovation, and promoting collaborative decision-making within school communities. Moreover, character formation has emerged as a foundational component of education, contributing to the holistic development of students and preparing them for success in various facets of life (Lickona, 2018).

Given the significance of these factors, understanding their synergistic effects on administrative leadership within the specific context

of secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat is paramount. Effective administrative leadership serves as a guiding framework for recruiting, developing, and retaining skilled personnel within the school. By aligning talent management practices with principles of advanced administrative leadership and character formation, secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat can enhance its capacity to attract, nurture, and retain high-quality educators and staff members. This alignment not only supports the professional growth of the faculty but also contributes to a positive organizational culture that prioritizes both educational excellence and ethical standards.

However, despite the recognized importance of advanced administrative leadership and character formation, limited empirical research has investigated their interconnectedness within the context of secondary public schools within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat. Consequently, there exists a gap in the literature regarding the specific strategies and practices that secondary public schools within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat can employ to optimize talent management while fostering a culture of leadership excellence and character development.

This study aims to determine the level of advanced administrative leadership and character formation, and to assess if there is a significant relationship between advanced administrative leadership and character formation among the personnel of these schools.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of advanced administrative leadership in a secondary public school within 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of:
 - 1.1. Strategic plans?
 - 1.2. Resource allocation?
 - 1.3. Risk management protocols?
 - 1.4. Delegation of power?
 - 1.5. Communication?
2. What is the extent of character formation among the personnel with in 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of:
 - 2.1. Values and attitudes?
 - 2.2. Culture and practices?
 - 2.3. Social environment?
 - 2.4. Career progression?
 - 2.5. Organizational commitment?
3. Is there a significant relationship between advanced administrative leadership and the character formation in a secondary public school with in 1st District of Sultan Kudarat?

Methodology

Research Design

The quantitative-descriptive method of research was used to gather information on the reactions of respondents of faculty and staff in a Secondary School and other relevant data in this study. A questionnaire was used in the data gathering. The study was evaluated by the respondents who are employed at Secondary Public School. As Creswell (2018) described, quantitative research tests objective theories by investigating variables' relationships. These variables can then be measured using instruments, resulting in numeric data that can be examined using statistical processes.

Participants

The study was conducted at secondary public schools within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat, with one hundred fourteen (114) randomly selected faculty and staff serving as respondents.

Instrument

The research instrument is designed and administered to the respondents in the Secondary Public School within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat. It comprises sets of questions that are validated. Pre-testing is conducted to establish the tool's reliability, where Cronbach Alpha is utilized. The reliability of a test is the degree of consistency of measurement that it gives. The test is given to the individual, and after the lapse of a certain length of time, the same test is again administered to the same individual. If the scores of the two administrations are identical or almost identical, the test is reliable (Hechanova & Hechanova, 2012).

To acquire the necessary data needed for the completion of the study, a survey questionnaire was distributed to the respondents. The questionnaire will consist of three (3) Sections containing questions about the respondents' demographic profile, level of administrative leadership practices at Secondary Public School, and work system. A Likert scale consisting of five options on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree), 2(disagree), 3 (neutral), 4 (Agree), and 5 (strongly agree) with corresponding quantitative descriptions will be used to measure both the level of administrative leadership practices and work system.

Procedure

In acquiring the necessary data from the respondents, the procedures were observed. First, the researcher proposed the study through the outline defense. After the approval, the formulation of survey tools was done and went through the validation and reliability test process. The communication letters were drafted and sent to concerned agencies which are part of the study. When everything was done, the survey administration was immediately performed with the identified respondents. With the data gathered, analyzed, and interpreted, the researcher started to draft the outputs for its find presentation.

Data Analysis

To provide a clear understanding of the study's focus and results, the following statistical treatments were applied:

The mean was used to determine the level of advanced administrative leadership and character formation in a secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat. This helped quantify the effectiveness of these practices across the schools. Additionally, the Pearson r correlation was employed to assess the significant relationship between advanced administrative leadership and character formation in these schools. This correlation analysis aimed to identify any meaningful connections between the two variables, providing deeper insights into their interrelationship. The findings are presented in various tables to thoroughly showcase the study results. The data were analyzed using a five-point Likert Rating Scale, along with descriptive ratings and verbal interpretations. This approach effectively represents the results related to advanced administrative leadership and character formation within the schools within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the data gathered during the study. It reveals the demographic profile of the faculty and staff, as well as the extent of advanced administrative leadership and character formation in secondary public schools within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat. Additionally, it explores the relationship between advanced administrative leadership and character formation within these schools.

Table 1. Respondents' Demographic Profiles

<i>Demographic Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Gender		
Male	50	43.86%
Female	64	56.14%
Educational Attainment		
College Graduate	82	71.93%
Masters Degree	30	26.32%
Doctorate Degree	2	1.75%
Age		
20-25 years old	5	4.39%
26-30 years old	15	13.16%
31-35 years old	20	17.54%
36-40 years old	40	35.09%
41-45 years old	26	22.81%
46-50 years old	5	4.39%
51-55 years old	3	2.63%
Marital Status		
Single	15	13.16%
Married	93	81.58%
Widowed	6	5.26%
Position		
Teacher I	12	10.53%
Teacher II	40	35.09%
Teacher III	50	43.86%
Master Teacher I	5	4.39%
Master Teacher II	1	0.88%
ADAS II	4	3.50%
AO II	2	1.75%
No. of years in service		
1-5 years	10	8.77%
6-10 years	35	30.70%
11-15 years	20	17.54%
16-20 years	21	18.42%
21 years and above	28	24.56%
Total	114	100%

The demographic profiles of the respondents, as presented in Table 1, reveal a diverse group characterized by various attributes such as gender, educational attainment, age, marital status, professional designation, and years of service. In terms of gender out of 114 respondents, 43.86% are male, accounting for 50 individuals, while the majorities, 56.14%, are female, totaling 64 individuals. This indicates a slightly higher female representation in the respondent pool. In terms of educational backgrounds of the respondents show a predominant presence of college graduates, making up 71.93% (82 individuals). Those holding a master’s degree constitute 26.32% (30 individuals), while a small fraction, 1.75% (2 individuals), and possess a doctorate degree. This distribution reflects a well-educated group with a significant number holding advanced degrees. In terms of age distribution spans across several age groups with the majority being within the 36-40 years old category, comprising 35.09% (40 individuals). The 26- 30 years old and 41-45 years old groups follow, representing 13.16% (15 individuals) and 22.81% (26 individuals) respectively. Other age categories include 20-25 years old at 4.39% (5 individuals), 31-35 years old at 17.54% (20 individuals), 46-50 years old at 4.39% (5 individuals), and 51-55 years old at 2.63% (3 individuals). This indicates a workforce with a broad range of age groups, though skewing slightly towards the mid- career age range.

In terms of marital status, a significant majority of the respondents are married, accounting for 81.58% (93 individuals). Single respondents constitute 13.16% (15 individuals), and widowed respondents make up 5.26% (6 individuals). This data suggests a predominantly married respondent demographic. In terms of current positions, the majority are classified as Teacher II, constituting 43.86% (50 individuals). This is followed by Teacher I at 35.09% (40 individuals), Tournament Manager at 10.53% (12 individuals), Teacher III at 4.39% (5 individuals), and Master Teacher I at 0.88% (1 individual). Additionally, Master Teacher II, ADAS II, and AO II are represented by smaller proportions of 3.50% (4 individuals) and 1.75% (2 individuals) respectively. This reflects a diverse range of teaching positions and a notable number of mid-level teaching staff. In terms of number of years in service, respondents have varied lengths of tenure. Those with 6-10 years of service represent 30.70% (35 individuals), followed by 21 years and above at 24.56% (28 individuals). Individuals with 16-20 years of service account for 18.42% (21 individuals), those with 11-15 years make up 17.54% (20 individuals), and the least experienced group, with 1-5 years of service, comprises 8.77% (10 individuals). This data highlights a mix of both experienced and relatively new employees, with a significant proportion having substantial years of service.

The Extent of Advanced Administrative Leadership

The extent of advanced administrative leadership in secondary public school within the 1st district of Sultan Kudarat, Evaluating the extent of these practices helps determine their impact on the overall performance and efficiency of the institution. It encompasses various aspects such as strategic plan, resource allocation, risk management protocol, delegation of power and the communication. Effective administrative leadership can enhance organizational clarity, foster collaboration, improve operational efficiency, and increase staff satisfaction, ultimately leading to a more productive and harmonious work environment. The following tables reveal the extent of advanced administrative leadership within the 1st District school of Sultan Kudarat in terms of strategic plan, resource allocation, risk management protocol, delegation of power and the communication.

Table 2. *Extent of Advanced Administrative Leadership in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Strategic Plans*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation	
1. The understanding of the long-term goals outlined in the organization's strategic plans is evident.	114	4.12	0.84	The Leadership is evident	Administrative highly
2. A level of involvement exists in the development of the organization's strategic plans.	114	4.11	0.77	The Leadership is evident	Administrative highly
3. Regular updates on the progress of initiatives aligned with the organization's strategic plans are consistently provided.	114	3.97	0.85	The Leadership is evident	Administrative highly
4. The belief is held that the strategic plans address current challenges and opportunities within the organization.	114	4.11	0.84	The Leadership is evident	Administrative highly
5. The alignment between strategic plans and daily operations within the organization is assessed.	114	4.19	0.74		
Grand Mean		4.10	0.81	The Leadership is evident	Administrative highly

The data from Table 2 reveals the extent of advanced administrative leadership in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat concerning strategic plans. Among the five indicators evaluated by 114 respondents, the top three results include alignment between strategic plans and daily operations (mean score: 4.19), understanding of long-term goals (mean score: 4.12), and involvement in plan development (mean score: 4.11). These high scores signify strong integration of strategic plans into daily activities, clear comprehension of long-term objectives, and active participation in plan formulation, reflecting robust administrative leadership.

Conversely, the provision of regular updates on initiative progress received the lowest score, with a mean of 3.97. While still indicating a high level of leadership, this score suggests room for improvement in maintaining consistent communication about the progress of strategic initiatives.

Brown and Chisholm, (2019), emphasize the significance of aligning strategic plans with daily operations for organizational effectiveness and employee commitment. Additionally, inclusive planning processes that engage stakeholders are highlighted as critical for successful leadership in educational settings (Smith & Adams, 2018). The importance of regular progress updates is underscored, as they contribute to transparency and momentum in plan execution (Johnson & Clark, 2021).

Table 3. *Extent of Advanced Administrative Leadership in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Resource Allocation*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. The organization prioritizes resource allocation to support its strategic goals.	114	4.04	0.76	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
2. There are resources available for the organization to achieve its objectives.	114	4.09	0.60	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
3. Overall satisfaction with the current process for allocating resources within the organization is high.	114	3.89	0.72	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
4. The allocation of resources in the organization is perceived as fair and equitable.	114	3.86	0.69	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
5. Resource allocation decisions in the organization are frequently based on sound evidence and analysis.	114	3.86	0.69	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
Grand Mean		3.95	0.69	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident.

The data in Table 3 evaluates the Advanced Administrative Leadership in secondary public school within the 1st district of Sultan Kudarat regarding resource allocation. Five indicators were assessed: prioritizing resource allocation for strategic goals, resource availability, satisfaction with the allocation process, perceived fairness and equity, and evidence-based allocation decisions. Each indicator received high mean scores ranging from 3.86 to 4.09, with a grand mean of 3.95, all interpreted as "highly evident" leadership. This consistency indicates that the school's administration is effective in prioritizing, ensuring, and fairly allocating resources, maintaining stakeholder satisfaction, and making evidence-based decisions.

Overall, the administrative leadership in resource allocation is perceived as highly effective, contributing to the school's success. These findings are supported by recent research, which emphasizes the importance of strategic resource management in educational leadership to enhance organizational performance and stakeholder satisfaction (Smith & Adams, 2019; Johnson & Nguyen, 2020).

Table 4 evaluates the extent of Advanced Administrative Leadership in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat regarding Risk Management Protocols. Five key indicators were assessed: the presence of a formalized risk management protocol, regular assessment and documentation of potential risks, clearly defined responsibility for overseeing risk management, proactive identification and evaluation of risks, and the effectiveness of mitigation strategies. Each indicator received high mean scores, ranging from 3.99 to 4.23, with a grand mean of 4.13, all interpreted as "The Administrative Leadership is highly evident."

These results indicate that the administration has established a robust risk management framework, regularly assesses and documents risks, clearly defines responsibilities, proactively identifies and evaluates potential risks, and implements effective mitigation strategies. This consistent and effective risk management is crucial for organizational stability and safety, as highlighted by recent research (Brown & Smith, 2019; Johnson & Thompson, 2021). Overall, the administrative leadership in risk management within the 1st District School

of Sultan Kudarat is perceived as highly effective, contributing significantly to the school's ability to manage and mitigate risks proactively and efficiently.

Table 4. *Extent of Advanced Administrative Leadership in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Risk Management Protocol*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. The organization has a formalized risk management protocol in place.	114	3.99	0.86	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
2. Potential risks are regularly assessed and documented within the organization.	114	4.12	0.86	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
3. Responsibility for overseeing the risk management process is clearly defined within the organization.	114	4.18	0.82	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
4. The organization identifies and evaluates risks before they escalate into major issues.	114	4.12	0.86	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
5. The organization's mitigation strategies effectively address identified risks.	114	4.23	0.84	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
Grand Mean		4.13	0.85	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident

Table 5 evaluates the extent of advanced administrative leadership in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat concerning the delegation of power. The highest mean score among the indicators is for the balance between centralized and decentralized decision-making, which scored a 4.31 with a standard deviation of 0.73. This high score indicates that the administration is particularly effective in maintaining this balance, a crucial aspect for ensuring both oversight and flexibility within the organization. Effective balance in decision-making processes helps in optimizing resource allocation, enhancing responsiveness to issues, and fostering a collaborative environment (Silva & Martins, 2019). The relatively moderate standard deviation reflects that while most respondents agree on this point, there is still some variability in perception, which is natural given the complexity of balancing these decision-making processes.

Table 5. *Extent of Advanced Administrative Leadership secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Delegation of Power*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. The transparency of the power delegation process within the organization is evident.	114	4.09	0.85	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
2. Responsibilities and authority are delegated based on individual competence and expertise.	114	4.08	0.63	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
3. The administration maintains a balance between centralized and decentralized decision-making within the organization.	114	4.31	0.73	The Administrative Leadership is greatly evident
4. Clear mechanisms are established for accountability regarding delegated responsibilities within the organization.	114	4.28	0.79	The Administrative Leadership is greatly evident
5. Empowerment is felt to make decisions within one's area of responsibility within the organization.	114	4.11	0.65	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
Grand Mean		4.17	0.73	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident

On the other hand, the lowest mean score is for competence-based delegation, which received a mean of 4.08 and a standard deviation of 0.63. Although this score is still high and indicates that delegating responsibilities based on individual competence is highly evident, it is the lowest among the evaluated indicators. This lower score, in comparison to others, might suggest room for improvement in ensuring that all stakeholders recognize and perceive the competence-based delegation process consistently. Lower variability in responses (indicated by the standard deviation) shows that there is a stronger consensus on this indicator, though it may benefit from further clarity or reinforcement to match the higher levels seen in other areas.

Overall, these findings highlight that while the school excels in maintaining a balanced decision-making approach, further attention could be directed toward enhancing the visibility and effectiveness of competence-based delegation. Strengthening these areas can lead to more effective and perceived equitable delegation practices, ultimately contributing to better organizational performance (Lee & Lee, 2020; Ghavifekr & Ibrahim, 2018).

Table 6. *Extent of extent of Advanced Administrative Leadership secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Communication*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Satisfaction is felt with the frequency of communication regarding important updates and decisions of the organization to the internal and external stakeholders.	114	4.19	0.81	Administrative Leadership is highly evident
2. Disseminates information to all staff members within the organization.	114	4.21	0.81	The Administrative Leadership is greatly evident
3. There is a channel of communication to all faculty and staff for feedback.	114	4.26	0.89	The Administrative Leadership is greatly evident
4. The School Transparency Board is visible and maintained in communication regarding decisions made by the administration within the organization.	114	4.15	0.85	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
5. Communication fosters a sense of collaboration and teamwork among staff members within the organization as well as the external stakeholders.	114	4.00	0.73	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
6. Regular conduct of SMEPA every quarter.	114	4.04	0.78	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
7. Conduct of PTA every quarter.	114	3.95	0.81	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
8. Conduct of SGC meeting and forum.	114	3.9	0.74	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
Grand Mean		4.09	0.80	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident

Table 6 evaluates the extent of advanced administrative leadership in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of communication. The highest mean score among the indicators is for the presence of a communication channel for feedback, which scored 4.26 with a standard deviation of 0.89. This high score indicates that the administration is particularly effective in providing avenues for feedback, which is crucial for continuous improvement and fostering an open communication culture. The relatively higher standard deviation reflects some variability in perceptions, suggesting that while many respondents recognize this channel, experiences may vary. This finding aligns with recent research emphasizing the importance of feedback mechanisms in educational institutions for enhancing communication effectiveness and organizational performance (Lee & Lee, 2020; Ghavifekr & Ibrahim, 2018).

On the other hand, the lowest mean scores are for the conduct of PTA meetings and SGC (School Governing Council) meetings and forums, both of which received a mean score of 3.95 with standard deviations of 0.81 and 0.74, respectively. Although these scores still indicate that administrative leadership is highly evident, they are the lowest among the evaluated indicators. These lower scores might suggest room for improvement in ensuring that these meetings are perceived as effective and valuable by all stakeholders. The relatively low standard deviations indicate a moderate level of agreement among respondents on these points. Further research could

explore strategies to enhance the effectiveness of PTA and SGC meetings, considering their importance in school governance and stakeholder engagement (Silva & Martins, 2019).

Table 7. *Summary on the of Advance Administrative Leadership of Faculty and Staff*

Leadership Effectiveness	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
Delegation of Power	4.17	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
Risk Management Protocol	4.13	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
Strategic Plans	4.10	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
Communication	4.09	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident
Resource Allocation	3.95	The Administrative Leadership is highly evident

Table 7 summarizes the effects of advanced administrative leadership among the faculty and staff in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat. The areas investigated include strategic plans, resource allocation, risk management protocol, delegation of power, and communication.

The highest mean score, 4.17, pertains to delegation of power, indicating that the faculty and staff perceive the leadership's delegation practices as highly effective. Effective delegation empowers staff by distributing responsibilities and decision-making authority, fostering an environment of trust and autonomy. Recent leadership experts like Daniel Goleman and Richard Boyatzis emphasize the importance of empowering team members to enhance organizational performance through emotional and social intelligence (Goleman & Boyatzis, 2018).

Risk management protocol received a mean score of 4.13, reflecting a high level of perceived leadership effectiveness. This suggests that the leadership is seen as proficient in identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks, ensuring organizational stability and resilience. Modern management experts such as David Hillson highlight the importance of proactive risk management in maintaining organizational health and resilience (Hillson, 2020).

Strategic plans, with a mean score of 4.10, also indicate a high level of perceived leadership effectiveness. This reflects the leadership's capability in setting clear, long-term objectives and devising comprehensive strategies to achieve them. Recent thought leaders like Rita McGrath emphasize the need for dynamic strategic planning to adapt to changing environments and sustain growth (McGrath, 2019).

Communication received a mean score of 4.09, indicating a high level of perceived leadership effectiveness. Effective communication channels ensure that all staff members are well-informed and can collaborate efficiently, enhancing overall productivity and morale. Contemporary leadership authorities like Amy Edmondson underscore the necessity of clear, consistent, and transparent communication to build psychological safety and effective teamwork (Edmondson, 2019).

Resource allocation, with a mean score of 3.95, while still indicating a high level of perceived leadership effectiveness, is the lowest among the surveyed areas. This suggests that the leadership is seen as proficient in managing and distributing resources efficiently to support various initiatives and operations. Experts such as Scott Galloway stress the critical role of resource management in achieving organizational goals and maintaining competitive advantage in the current economic climate (Galloway, 2020).

Overall, the data from the survey indicates that the administrative leadership practices within the 1st District School of Sultan Kudarat are perceived positively by the faculty and staff. Each area surveyed shows a high level of effectiveness, with delegation of power being particularly strong. These practices contribute to a well-organized and productive environment, which is essential for the school's success and the professional satisfaction of its staff.

The extent of Character Formation

The success of secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat relies heavily on the character formation of its faculty and staff. This study explores how well the school's personnel develop in terms of values and attitudes, culture and practices, social environment, career progression, and organizational commitment. Understanding these aspects helps reveal their impact on the school's environment and overall performance.

Effective character formation leads to ethical behavior, positive culture, improved interactions, and strong commitment, resulting in a productive and harmonious work environment. This research aims to provide insights into these dimensions and suggest ways to enhance professional and personal growth among the staff.

Table 8. *Extent of Character Formation in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Values and Attitudes*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Promotes a culture of kindness and understanding among its personnel.	114	4.25	0.83	The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of character formation
2. Staff members demonstrate respect and empathy towards students, colleagues, and the school community.	114	4.19	0.89	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
3. Personnel are encouraged to demonstrate compassion and empathy with others.	114	4.11	0.86	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
4. Teachers demonstrate high moral values.	114	4.09	0.78	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
5. There is an emphasis on positive values and attitudes among personnel	114	3.97	0.78	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
Grand Mean	114	4.12	0.80	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation

Table 8 evaluates the degree of character development in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat concerning values and attitudes. The highest mean score, 4.25, is attributed to the promotion of a culture of kindness and understanding, indicating the school's strong commitment to nurturing a supportive and compassionate environment vital for student well-being and overall school climate. This aligns with recent research emphasizing the importance of positive school culture in fostering student success and well-being (Durlak et al., 2018).

Conversely, the lowest mean score, 3.97, pertains to the emphasis on positive values and attitudes among personnel, signaling a potential area for enhancement in reinforcing these values among staff members. Recent studies underscore the significance of staff modeling positive behaviors for student character development and academic success (Taylor et al., 2020). This suggests the need for targeted interventions to strengthen the cultivation of positive values and attitudes among school personnel.

Table 9. *Extent of Character Formation in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Culture and Practices*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Staff members feel valued and respected for their unique contributions and perspectives.	114	4.06	0.88	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
2. There is a sense of inclusivity and diversity celebrated within the school's culture.	114	4.03	0.72	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
3. Promotes cultural awareness and appreciation among its personnel.	114	3.99	0.84	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
4. The school fosters a culture of collaboration and teamwork among its personnel.	114	3.95	0.81	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
5. Creates are for professional opportunities and relationship building.	114	3.92	0.79	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
Grand Mean	114	3.99	0.81	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation

Table 9 assesses the degree of character development in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat concerning its cultural values and practices. The indicator with the highest mean score, 4.03, pertains to the celebration of inclusivity and diversity

within the school's culture. This suggests a strong emphasis on fostering an environment that embraces diversity, crucial for cultivating a sense of belonging and equity among both staff and students. This finding is consistent with recent literature highlighting the importance of inclusivity in educational settings for promoting positive social outcomes and academic success (Denson & Chang, 2020).

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean score, 3.92, focuses on creating opportunities for professional development and relationship building. While the score still reflects a relatively high level of character formation, it underscores a potential area for improvement in providing avenues for staff to enhance their professional growth and forge meaningful connections within the school community. Recent studies emphasize the significance of professional development programs in fostering teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction, ultimately contributing to improved student outcomes (Lieberman & Pointer Mace, 2018). Thus, addressing this aspect may further enhance the school's efforts in character formation and overall organizational effectiveness.

Table 10. *Extent of Character Formation in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Social Environment*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Opportunities for social interaction and bonding among staff members are encouraged and facilitated.	114	4.19	0.85	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
2. The school actively addresses and resolves conflicts in a constructive manner.	114	4.05	0.95	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
3. The school promotes a sense of camaraderie and solidarity among its personnel through team-building activities.	114	4.05	0.87	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
4. Staff members are free to express their opinions and concerns in a respectful environment.	114	4.00	0.84	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
5. The school provides a supportive and nurturing social environment for its personnel.	114	3.98	0.83	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
Grand Mean	114	4.06	0.87	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation

Table 10 evaluates the extent of character formation in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of its social environment. The highest mean score, 4.19, is for encouraging and facilitating opportunities for social interaction and bonding among staff members.

This high score highlights the school's commitment to fostering a positive and cohesive social environment, which is essential for staff morale and collaboration. This finding aligns with recent research emphasizing the importance of social interactions and bonding in creating a positive workplace culture and enhancing job satisfaction (Sonnetag & Fritz, 2018).

On the other hand, the lowest mean score, 3.98, is for providing a supportive and nurturing social environment for personnel. Although this score still indicates a high level of character formation, it suggests that there is room for improvement in creating an even more supportive and nurturing atmosphere for staff. Recent studies highlight that a supportive social environment is crucial for reducing stress and increasing overall job satisfaction and performance (Bakker et al., 2020).

Table 11 assesses the extent of character formation in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in relation to career progression. The indicators include opportunities for professional development and growth, career advancement support, recognition and rewards for contributions, mentorship programs, and opportunities for skill enhancement and specialization.

The highest mean score, 4.25, is related to the support staff receives in advancing their careers and achieving professional goals. This score indicates that the school is particularly effective in facilitating career progression, which is vital for maintaining staff motivation and satisfaction. Recent studies underscore the importance of career support in enhancing job satisfaction and professional growth (Ng & Feldman, 2018).

Conversely, the lowest mean score, 4.09, pertains to opportunities for skill enhancement and specialization. While this score still reflects a high level of character formation, it suggests that there is room for improvement in providing staff with ample opportunities to develop specialized skills. Research shows that ongoing opportunities for skill enhancement are essential for staff retention and performance (Tims et al., 2019).

Table 11. *Extent of Character Formation in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Career Progression*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Staff members are supported in advancing their careers and achieving their professional goals.	114	4.25	0.85	The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of character formation
2. The school provides opportunities for professional development and growth for its personnel.	114	4.19	0.95	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
3. The school recognizes and rewards the contributions and achievements of its personnel.	114	4.18	0.82	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
4. The school offers mentorship programs to support staff members in their career progression.	114	4.14	0.79	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
5. Opportunities for skill enhancement and specialization are readily available to personnel.	114	4.09	0.76	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
Grand Mean	114	4.17	0.83	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation

Table 12 examines character formation in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat regarding organizational commitment. The highest mean scores, both at 4.32, are for staff commitment to the school's goals and mission, and for personnel working beyond their regular duties. These high scores reflect a particularly strong organizational commitment among the staff, showcasing their dedication and willingness to contribute beyond their formal responsibilities. Research has demonstrated that high levels of organizational commitment are associated with increased job satisfaction and performance (Meyer, Stanley, & Vandenberg, 2018).

Table 12. *Extent of Character Formation in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat in terms of Organizational Commitment*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Staff members demonstrate a strong commitment to the goals and mission of the school.	114	4.32	0.84	The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of character formation
2. Personnel work beyond their regular duties.	114	4.32	0.87	The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of character formation
3. There is a sense of loyalty and dedication among personnel towards the school's objectives.	114	4.21	0.81	The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of character formation
4. Staff members actively participate in school-wide initiatives and events to support the organization's mission and vision.	114	4.19	0.81	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
5. The school promotes a culture of accountability and responsibility among its personnel.	114	4.14	0.79	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
Grand Mean	114	4.24	0.82	The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of character formation

In contrast, the lowest mean score, 4.14, pertains to the school's promotion of a culture of accountability and responsibility among its personnel. Although this score still indicates a high level of character formation, it suggests an area where the school could further enhance its efforts.

Promoting a strong culture of accountability is essential for maintaining high performance standards and fostering trust within the organization (Wang & Hsieh, 2020).

Table 13. Summary on the Effects of Advance Administrative Leadership on the Character Formation of Faculty and Staff

Character Formation	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
Organizational Commitment	4.24	The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of character formation
Career Progression	4.17	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
Values and Attitudes	4.12	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
Social Environment	4.06	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation
Culture and Practices	3.99	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of character formation

Table 13 summarizes the impact of advanced administrative leadership on character formation among faculty and staff in secondary public school within the 1st District of Sultan Kudarat across various areas, including values and attitudes, culture and practices, social environment, career progression, and organizational commitment. The highest mean score of 4.24 is for organizational commitment, indicating an excellent level of character formation with strong loyalty and dedication to the school's mission and goals. Career progression received a mean score of 4.17, reflecting effective support for professional growth and development. Values and attitudes scored 4.12, showing an emphasis on fostering positive values and attitudes. The social environment received a mean score of 4.06, highlighting a supportive and nurturing atmosphere. Although culture and practices had the lowest mean score of 3.99, it still indicates a high level of character formation, suggesting a collaborative and inclusive culture with room for further enhancement.

Overall, advanced administrative leadership positively impacts character formation within the 1st District School of Sultan Kudarat, with particularly strong organizational commitment. These practices create a supportive and professional environment conducive to personal and professional growth.

The Analysis of Advanced Administrative Leadership and Character Formation

The effectiveness of administrative leadership practices is crucial for the performance and efficiency of work systems in educational settings. To investigate this relationship within the 1st District School of Sultan Kudarat, a statistical analysis was conducted to determine the correlation between these two variables. Table 16 provides an overview of this relationship, highlighting the strength and significance of the correlation. The findings offer insights into how improvements in administrative leadership can enhance the overall work system, thereby supporting the institution's operational success.

Table 14. Degree of Relationship between Administrative Leadership Practices and Work System

Pair of Variable	N	R	P-value
Advanced Administrative Leadership and Character Formation	114	0.884**	0.000

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 14 discuss the analysis of the relationship between the variables "administrative leadership practices" and "character formation" reveals a very strong positive correlation, as indicated by a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.884. This high correlation coefficient suggests that there is a strong linear relationship between the two variables, meaning that as the value of "administrative leadership practices" increases, the value of "character formation" tends to increase as well.

The significance of this correlation was assessed using a two-tailed test with a significance level of 0.05. The resulting p-value for the correlation between "administrative leadership practices" and "character formation" is 0.000. Since this p-value is below the 0.05 threshold, we can conclude that the correlation is statistically significant. This implies that the observed relationship between "administrative leadership's practices" and "character formation" is highly unlikely to be due to random chance, thereby affirming the reliability of the correlation in this context.

These results are based on a sample size of 114 observations, providing a robust dataset for the analysis. The strong and significant correlation suggests that there is a meaningful relationship between the administrative leadership practices and the character formation under study, which could be a key insight for further research and practical applications in this field.

In the context of this dissertation, these findings align with prior research emphasizing the crucial role of administrative leadership in

shaping organizational dynamics (Smith, 2020; Johnson, 2019). While previous studies have primarily focused on organizational efficiency and effectiveness, the significant correlation observed between administrative leadership practices and character formation within the 1st District School of Sultan Kudarat underscores their profound influence on personal and professional development within educational institutions (Brown, 2018; Lee, 2017).

These results suggest that effective administrative leadership not only enhances operational performance but also cultivates positive values, attitudes, and ethical behavior among faculty and staff. Such outcomes resonate with broader educational research highlighting the transformative impact of leadership on organizational culture and climate (Davis, 2019; Wilson, 2016). The robust correlation identified in this study supports the hypotheses proposed, affirming that administrative improvements can significantly contribute to fostering a supportive and ethical environment conducive to both staff satisfaction and student success.

Conclusions

Based on these findings, several conclusions can be drawn;

Firstly, the advanced administrative leadership within the 1st District School of Sultan Kudarat is highly effective in fostering communication, which promotes collaboration and teamwork among faculty and staff. The delegation of power is robust, empowering staff and enabling them to take initiative. The school's strong risk management and strategic planning capabilities ensure stability and continuous improvement.

However, there is a need for better resource allocation to maximize benefits. The positive character formation among faculty and staff is significantly influenced by the effective leadership practices in place, emphasizing values such as kindness, respect, and empathy. The strong correlation between leadership practices and character formation underscores the critical role of effective leadership in shaping the school's overall environment.

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